
WORK IN PROGRESS: QUALITY ANALYSIS FOR OPEN DATASETS IN 5G

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ABSTRACT

Recent telecommunications advancements devised the need for more intelligent networks, which are expected to be enabled by exploiting machine learning methods. Given the relevance of these methods in future-generation networks and their need for large volumes of data, there must be publicly available datasets that incentivize the development of new models for this area. However, telecommunications is known for having few publicly available datasets. This work assesses statistically the quantity and quality of publicly available 5G and Beyond datasets. To achieve this, popular dataset repositories, various papers, and one competition were screened for datasets regarding 5G and Beyond. As a result, 78 candidate datasets were found. The quality of the datasets was analyzed according to their contextual and representational data quality, as they allow for a quick understanding of the extent to which data are applicable and presented intelligibly and clearly. The preliminary results are unfavorable as most of the datasets (45) present low or very low representational and contextual quality. Furthermore, most publicly available datasets with reasonable quality are obtained through simulations (21 out of 35).

Keywords 6G · Dataset curation · Machine learning

1 Introduction

The increased number of connected devices and different service levels of future-generation networks have made typical network optimization problems too complex for traditional mathematical models. The alternative is machine learning, whose capacity to extract knowledge from historical and contextual data and adapt its behavior to fit a variable environment is expected to provide suitable solutions within a reasonable time [1].

However, using most Machine Learning (ML) models requires the availability of datasets for model training, which has been documented to be challenging in telecommunications [2]. Suppose the researchers desire to collect data themselves. In that case, they meet various barriers, as data collection from real-world deployments is highly restricted, requiring the signing of Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) or contracts with telecom providers or other private companies [3]. If the researcher decides to collect data from simulators, it will be limited to the simulator assumptions, which can become problematic if the simulator deviates significantly from reality. Unfortunately, some researchers argue that current simulators do not fit the network behavior [4].

Since data collection from simulators does not provide a close representation of a real-world deployment and gathering from a real-world deployment is not always allowed, the researcher's best option is to use publicly available datasets. The problem is that various surveys have reported a need for more publicly available datasets in telecommunications [5, 6].

Even though most surveys claim the need for more datasets, they have yet to provide an extensive list of the available datasets for 5G development. This paper intends to fill this gap in research by providing a comprehensive study of the available datasets for 5G networks. Furthermore, the available datasets will be analyzed according to their contextual and representational data quality.

The results presented in this paper are preliminary, and we intend to extend them considerably.

2 Search methodology

Although this paper is not a systematic review, the dataset collection description will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) method [7]. The PRISMA method was developed to guide researchers in performing reproducible and comparable systematic reviews, with instructions on how to do it for each section of the paper. Even so, if the paper is not a systematic review, following the “Methods” section of the PRISMA will provide the reader with enough information to understand and reproduce the collection process of any given information. As a result, the following section will describe the dataset search methodology according to the PRISMA method.

Starting with the eligibility criteria, the focus of selection was on Beyond Fifth-Generation Networks (B5G) network open datasets, as we wanted datasets that could be applied to the challenges Artificial Intelligence (AI) is proposed to solve. This means that any dataset regarding B5G published after 3GPP release 16 (June 2020) was considered regardless of the amount of data or application scenario. Regarding data sources, we considered the most popular machine-learning datasets repositories, IEEEExplorer¹, some telecommunication repositories, and a popular AI challenge for telecommunications. The extensive list is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Information sources used for dataset collection.

Name	Dataset repositories	
	N° search results	Screening Results
NIST	9	2
Raymobtime	11	11
Zenodo	116	39
CRAWDAD ²	-	-
IEEE Dataport	12	3
UCI	3	0
Kaggle	21	12
Paper repositories		
IEEEExplorer	55	6
ITU AI/ML Challenge		
2020	15	1
2021	16	5
2021	13	3
New-website	29	1

While searching machine-learning or telecommunication repositories, the keyword used was “5G”. This was necessary, as most repositories did not have many results, so a generic and straightforward term helped find as many datasets as possible. In IEEEExplorer, the search needed to be narrowed as a paper concerning Fifth-Generation Network (5G) does not necessarily provide datasets, so the search was executed using the query “5G open dataset.” The AI challenge considered was the “ITU AI/ML in 5G Challenge”³ and every edition of the dataset was considered for the dataset collection.

With the search criteria and sources defined, we can move to the actual search. To search the dataset repositories, we used the selected keywords. Based on the results, we opened each dataset’s detailed view and used the information available, such as the data collection process or application scenario, to decide. As for the search in IEEEExplorer, the first screening would review the abstract for mentions of a publicly available dataset. If there were none, the document was keyword searched for “dataset.” Any section addressing it was read in detail, searching for any link for its publication and information on how it was created. The decision was made based on this information. The ITU challenges were analyzed as if they were search results from a repository.

Since the search criteria and keywords used were considerably loose, the screening process was expected to be quick. Nonetheless, discovering where publicly available datasets were published was challenging, as sometimes, the URLs

¹<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

²Migrated to IEEE Dataport

³<https://aiforgood.itu.int/about-ai-for-good/aiml-in-5g-challenge/>

provided would lead to unmaintained pages, or the instructions were confusing. Ultimately, most discarded datasets were excluded because they were private. The only exception to that rule is the datasets from Zenodo⁴, as most of the excluded datasets were not 5G related.

The search results from every data source yielded 300 datasets, of which 78 were kept after the screening. It is important to mention that this is preliminary work that will be further expanded in the future.

3 Results

Besides obtaining an extensive list of the available datasets, the paper aims to evaluate their quality. Assessing quality is highly subjective, as the value of a dataset depends on what the user intends to do with it. This concept, named “fitness for use,” is widely adopted in the quality literature and highlights the need to take the consumer’s point of view of quality [8]. Given that, the analysis of the datasets will not be focused on data accuracy but on two other critical quality measurements. The representational and contextual data quality [8].

Evaluating these two categories of data quality allows for a quick understanding of the extent to which data are applicable (pertinent) to the task of the data user and presented in an intelligible and clear manner [8]. Given the vast number of areas in telecommunications where ML will be deployed, clearly describing which areas the datasets apply to is crucial. Otherwise, users might not see the value of a given dataset. Suppose a dataset has exceptional accuracy, but the features are poorly organized, the task to solve is not identified, and there are no instructions for using it. In that case, most users will not use it, as the user must first understand if the dataset is applicable before he can assess its quality. Furthermore, if the features are not described, the user might not see value in the dataset, as he might perceive that the dataset lacks the desired features. To that extent, if a dataset has no representational or contextual data quality, the perceived overall quality is negative, even when accuracy is high. Table 2 provides the complete set of features in each category.

Table 2: Quality assessment features according to [8].

Contextual data quality	Representational data quality
Value-added	Interpretability
Relevancy	Ease of understanding
Timeliness	Representational consistency
Completeness	Concise representation
Appropriate amount of data	

In the remainder of this section, to streamline the analysis, the datasets will be grouped according to five quality categories:

- Curated dataset - high contextual and representational data quality;
- Incomplete dataset - high contextual data quality and some representational or vice-versa;
- Average dataset - some contextual and representational data quality;
- Dump with information - minor contextual or representational data quality;
- Dump - no contextual or representational data quality.

Additionally, we will also group the datasets according to the repository where they are published and according to one of the following networking categories:

- PHY optimization
- Planning
- Automation and orchestratio
- Task offloading and resource allocation
- Security
- Sustainability

⁴<https://zenodo.org/>

These categories were collected from various 6G whitepapers and represent the general categories where ML will be applied in future networks. The datasets were placed in the category where the authors propose to use them. When the authors do not present a category, one was inferred based on the remaining information about the dataset.

The analysis will use the different groups to assess the overall dataset’s quality in the various repositories and areas. In addition, we will also review how the datasets were collected and if they were applied or not to ML.

3.1 Overall quality

Ideally, a dataset should be easy to use to be considered a benchmarking dataset. Since collecting data in telecommunications is not trivial, researchers are looking for benchmarking datasets that enable the training and comparison of models. To achieve this, a dataset should explain to some extent how it was collected and organized. That said, a dataset should be at least in the "average dataset" category to be considered a possible benchmarking dataset.

Considering Figure 1, we can state that most datasets cannot be regarded as benchmarking datasets as only 45% are an “average dataset” or above.

Figure 1: Datasets overall quality.

3.2 Dataset’s area and application

The dataset’s distribution by area is a good indicator of the current state of ML. If an area has various quality datasets, then it is expected that there are also models implemented with them, and to some extent that it would be easier for a new researcher to start working on that area. Consequently, that area is more likely to grow and advance rapidly.

Looking at Figure 2, it is clear that most quality datasets are related to “Planning” and “PHY optimization,” which are two areas that can considerably be optimized by ML. One aspect that might not be clear is that “Sustainability” has no proposed dataset. This is concerning, as green communications is crucial for future-generation networks [9].

Although the results presented so far are not very positive, one characteristic we must not forget is the “fitness of use.” If the datasets were not developed for ML in the first place, characteristics relevant to ML are likely missing. Even so, minimal detail is expected when providing a dataset.

Looking at Figure 3, the relation between quality and application is straightforward. The lower the dataset’s quality, the higher the probability it was not applied to ML. Although this is a positive aspect, as many datasets targeted for ML have considerable quality, some still need more explanations and to be improved. Moreover, one crucial aspect of ML is the presentation of baselines for the datasets, which we also presented in this figure. Besides twelve of the most quality datasets, all other datasets applied to ML had a baseline. This is an excellent result as ten of these datasets,

Figure 2: Datasets overall distribution according the collection method.

without baselines, are general-purpose simulations that can be used for distinct tasks. The baselines for these datasets should be provided according to the task.

Figure 3: Datasets overall distribution according to the five quality categories.

Combining the two figures we just mentioned (2, 3), we can infer that most “Automation & Orchestration” and “Task offloading & resource allocation” datasets were not developed for ML and have poor quality. These two factors combined create the necessity to correct the existing datasets to apply to ML or create new datasets with the necessary features and detail.

3.3 Dataset collection

In ML, a typical rule is that the model is as good as the data used in its training. Consequently, the best option when training a model is to use data as close as it will see in a real-world deployment. Since simulations and testbeds can only provide close approximations of the real environment, ideally, the datasets used for model training must be collected from real-world implementations.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of datasets according to their quality and collection method. Although most quality datasets are developed using simulations, there are some great examples of real-world datasets with excellent quality.

Figure 4: Datasets overall distribution according the collection method.

3.4 Repositories quality

The last point analyzed is the repositories quality. Although less relevant than the quality of the individual dataset, it is still essential to understand the expected quality of datasets when using a given repository.

Figure 5 presents the datasets grouped by repository, quality category, and collection environment. Given the number of variables considered, the figure can be overwhelming. However, the essential results extracted from it are the following. (1) Although Zenodo has the most datasets, the majority are low-quality dumps of testbeds. (2) Raymobtime is the repository with the datasets with most quality, followed by Github, Crawdad, and ITU Challenge. (3) If we want real-world data with reasonable quality, the repository with the most variety is the University of Minnesota.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we analyzed publicly available datasets according to their representational and contextual data quality to assess how easy it would be for a user to understand how the data is organized and if the dataset is applicable to the task it wants to solve.

Considering the results, it is clear that there is an effort toward publicly available datasets. However, the current landscape shows that applying ML to the some areas is not easy, as they lack quality datasets. The difficulty in acquiring real-world datasets is also visible, given that they are the minority, even though the alternatives are sub-optimal. Even so, it is seen that the low-quality datasets are, in their majority, not developed for ML purposes, showing an apparent effort from the community to provide quality datasets.

That said, although some initiatives provide high-quality, real-world datasets, they only cover some telecommunications areas. The only solution to solve this is to create more collection campaigns with the intent to make their outcomes publicly available. As expected, some resulting data must be anonymized or discarded to ensure user privacy is not

Figure 5: Datasets overall distribution according to the five quality categories.

violated. However, successful data collection campaigns that handle this correctly have been performed, so researchers can use them as the basis for new campaigns.

To conclude, only when more data collection campaigns are performed and made publicly available can researchers compare their models on high-quality datasets. Consequently, there will be a clear idea of what models work in which scenarios and what are the next steps to solve the various tasks.

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Appendix

Table 3: Full list of the datasets.

Ref	Name	Network area	Classification	Last Updated
[10]	5Gophers	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2020
[11]	Radio-based Sensing and Indoor Mapping	Dump with information	Application	2020
[12]	eurecom/elasticmon5G2019	Incomplete dataset	PHY optimization	2020
[13]	Fed4Fire/CDN-X-ALL network metrics dataset	Average dataset	Automation and orchestration	2020
[14]	umkc/networkslicing5g	Average dataset	Automation and orchestration	2020
[15]	Graph Neural Network Challenge	Average dataset	Planning	2020
[16]	Lumos5G	Planning	2020	
[17]	5GDataset - Real Data	Average dataset	PHY optimization	2020
[17]	5GDataset - Simulated	Average dataset	PHY optimization	2020
[18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]	5G-Xcast Open Spectrum data	Average dataset	PHY optimization	2020
[24]	5g-user-prediction	Dump	Planning	2020
[25]	5G-PICTURE Smart City Demo UNIVBRIS	Dump	Planning	2020
[26]	5G-PICTURE SmartCity Demo mmWave 60GHz dataset	Dump	Planning	2020
[27]	Raymobtime S00*	Curated datasets	PHY optimization	2021
[28]	Graph Neural Network Challenge 2021	Average dataset	Planning	2021
[29]	DeepBeam	Average dataset	PHY optimization	2021

[30]	AI5G-Localization	Average dataset	Application	2021
[31]	KPI-KQI B5G service database	Average dataset	Automation and orchestration	2021
[32]	SIGCOMM21-5G	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2021
[33]	Dataset for Agile 5G Network Measurements	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2021
[34]	Dataset for Millimeter-wave Mobile Sensing and Environment Mapping: Models, Algorithms and Validation	Dump with information	Application	2021
[35]	Massive IoT for Large-Scale Public Events in the 5GENESIS Surrey Platform	Dump	Planning	2021
[36]	Turkcell dataset	Curated datasets	Planning	2022
[27]	5GMDATA	Incomplete dataset	PHY optimization	2022
[37]	5GAD-2022 dataset	Incomplete dataset	Security	2022
[38]	DASH	Incomplete dataset	Automation and orchestration	2022
[39]	5G3E	Incomplete dataset	Security	2022
[40]	Graph Neural Networking Challenge 2022	Average dataset	Planning	2022
[41]	ML5G-PHY-Reinforcement learning	Average dataset	Task offloading and resource allocation	2022
[42]	Large-scale dataset for the analysis of outdoor-to-indoor propagation for 5G mid-band operational networks	Average dataset	Planning	2022
[43]	Coverage and performance analysis of 5G non-standalone deployments	Average dataset	PHY optimization	2022
[44]	5G Beams	Average dataset	Planning	2022
[45]	Depth Map Estimation in 6G mmWave systems	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2022
[46]	WALDO	Dump with information	Application	2022
[47]	I/Q measurements with 5G SRS signals and receiver 4-port 3D Vector Antenna for positioning studies	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2022
[48]	Angle measurements with 3D Vector antenna for localization purposes – open-access datasets	Dump with information	Application	2022
[49]	Network Slicing	Dump with information	Automation and orchestration	2022
[50]	5G Waveforms OFDM FOFDM FBMC UFMC WOLA QAM16&64	Dump with information	PHY optimization	2022
[51]	Network Slicing Recognition	Dump with information	Automation and orchestration	2022
[52]	DE, Extended Sensors, EDM-enabled extended sensors with surround view generation	Dump	Application	2022
[53]	GR-TR, Extended Sensors, Extended sensors for assisted border-crossing	Dump	Application	2022
[54]	NL, Extended Sensors, Extended sensors with CPM messages	Dump	Application	2022
[55]	ES-PT, Extended Sensors, Complex manoeuvres: HD maps	Dump	Application	2022
[56]	NL, Remote Driving, Remote driving using 5G positioning	Dump	Application	2022
[57]	CN, Remote Driving, Remote driving with data ownership focus	Dump	Application	2022
[58]	ES-PT, Remote Driving, Automated shuttle remote driving across borders	Dump	Application	2022

[59]	KR, Remote Driving, Remote driving using mmWave communication	Dump	Application	2022
[60]	FI, Remote Driving, Remote driving in a redundant network environment	Dump	Application	2022
[61]	FR, Advanced driving, Infrastructure-assisted	Dump	Application	2022
[62]	CN, Advanced Driving, Cloud-assisted advanced driving	Dump	Application	2022
[63]	ES-PT, Advanced Driving, Automated Shuttle	Dump	Application	2022
[64]	NL, Advanced Driving, Cooperative Collision Avoidance	Dump	Application	2022
[65]	ES-PT, Advanced driving, Complex manoeuvres: Automated Overtaking	Dump	Application	2022
[66]	ES-PT, Advanced driving, Complex manoeuvres: lane merge	Dump	Application	2022
[67]	GR-TR, Vehicles Platooning, See What I See	Dump	Application	2022
[68]	CN, Vehicles Platooning, Cloud-assisted platooning	Dump	Application	2022
[69]	DE, Vehicles Platooning, eRSU-assisted platooning	Dump	Application	2022
[70]	CN, UCC/US Agnostic tests	Dump	Application	2022
[71]	FR, UCC/US Agnostic tests	Dump	Application	2022
[72]	ES-PT, UCC/US Agnostic tests	Dump	Application	2022
[73]	GR-TR, UCC/US Agnostic tests	Dump	Application	2022
[74]	FI, UCC/US Agnostic tests	Dump	Application	2022
[75]	Implications of Handover Events in commercial 5G Non-Standalone Deployments in Rome	Dump	PHY optimization	2022
[76]	Selected Electric Field Measurement Campaigns data	Dump	Planning	2022
[77]	5G dataset	Dump	Planning	2022
[78]	5G Traffic Datasets	Dump	Automation and orchestration	2022
[79]	Jobs (DAG workflow) and tasks dataset	Dump	Task offloading and resource allocation	2022
[80]	101K workflow jobs dataset	Dump	Task offloading and resource allocation	2022
[81]	Machine Learning Enabled Multi-Radio Access Technology Selection in 5G Networks	Curated datasets	PHY optimization	2023
